

EXPLANATION OF TRADE AND SALE RELATIONS DURING THE TEMURIAN PERIOD IN THE DIARY OF R. G. CLAVIKHO

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Abstract. In this article, Amir Temur and trade relations during the Timurid period are studied and analyzed on the example of Claviho's "Diary". Some comments about the daily life of the market, stalls and traders are given. Keywords. Claviho, "Kundalik", trade, Amir Temur, Timurids, stalls, bazaars, caravanserais.

INTRODUCTION. The establishment of a centralized state by Amir Temur had a great impact on the expansion of internal and external trade. In almost all cities and villages of the Sultanate, new stalls, bazaars, caravanserais were built, and caravan roads were repaired, as well as necessary conditions were created for merchants to trade safely. Valuable information about Amir Temur and trade relations of the Timurid period, the activities of merchants is also found in Claviho's "Diary".

LITERATURE ANALYSIS. Let's talk about the author here. On May 33, 1403, Claviho left the city of Cadiz, Spain, and after 15 months, he arrived in Samarkand in August 1404. After returning to Spain, the author submits to him in the form of a report what he saw in the places up to Samarkand for a period of 1 month. He also participated in the drafting of the king's will in the city of Toledo. He returned to Madrid in 1407 and died in 1412. His name was given to one of the streets of Madrid, and on January 27-29, 2003, during the visit of I.Karimov, the meeting with the mayor of Madrid took place here.

The first edition of the work was published in 1582 in Seville by Agrote

Published by Molina under the title "History of Buuk Temurlang". But Clavijo would not have published under such a name. It is noteworthy that he named Temurbek and not Temurlang. In the 71st chapter of the work, he gives the exact reasons and calls him Temurbek. In 1779, it was published by the Amirola publishing house in the 3rd volume of the collection of chronicles and memoirs devoted to the history of the Kingdom of Castile. In 1782, Antonio Sancha published it as a separate book. In 1943, "DIARS" was published in Spanish by the historian Ferdinand Lopez Estrada in Madrid. It should be said that it was also published in Japan, France, Russia, Argentina, Iran, and Turkey. Achil Togaev translated the work since 1987. In 1988-1900, it was regularly published in 15 issues of Sanat magazine. In 2006, Ulug'bek Joraev also published 174 articles, but O. Tugaev's translation is much more perfect. We also used this translation in our article.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION. On the initiative of Amir Temur and the princes, many mosques, madrasahs, palaces, khanaqahs, stalls, shops, workshops and other important buildings were built. The establishment of political and diplomatic relations with China, India, the Golden Horde, Mongolia and other countries has had an impact on trade relations.

In his work, Klavikho emphasizes that bazaars and stalls have been newly built in Samarkand, that they are finally prosperous, and that there is an abundance of all kinds of food in the

kingdom. In particular, he mentions that cereals and cereal products are very cheap. "Kundalik" notes that the price of 1 sheep is 1 ducat.

Also, while thinking about the markets in Samarkand, "They set up shops on both sides of the street, in front of every shop high stools covered with marble were installed. Top of the street is closed in the form of a dome, and there are holes through which light falls," wrote Klaviho. Skilled and well-known architects participated in the construction of stalls in Samarkand, and special attention was paid to expanding the city's trade opportunities.

CONCLUSION. It should be said that Amir Temur's prices in the markets, the entry and exit of products is controlled. For example, meat butchers who increased the price, shoemakers and shoemakers who increased the price of goods were sentenced to death.

An important aspect of "Kundalik" is that the author compares the prices of food products in this era to those in Spanish markets.

In particular, in Samarkand, a pair of sheep costs one ducat (a Spanish coin), cattle cost one and a half fanegas (the unit of weight is about half a kilo), barley costs half a real (a unit of measure for grain products), and products such as flour and rice are very cheap. Also, there were many craftsmen in the city. Of course, skilled in the development of trade artisans had a special place. During his military trips, Amir Temur brought mature specialists of his field to the kingdom. Clavijo, speaking about this, says that they brought from Turkey bow and arrow makers, stone washers, goldsmiths, silk weavers from Damascus, and masters who made bows and other weapons. It should be noted that 100-150 thousand representatives of various fields brought by Amir Temur. According to Ibn Arabshah, rope weavers started growing hemp and flax plants in the country and prepared raw materials for themselves. Turkish, Arab, Moorish, Armenian, Greek and other nationalities were among the craftsmen.

In conclusion, it should be said that during the time of Amir Temur the creation of a centralized state, in turn, led to the development of internal and external trade, the improvement of the life of the urban and rural population, and the revival of relations with other foreign countries.

References:

1. Rui Gonzalez de Clavijo. Diary of a trip to Amir Temur's palace in Samarkand (1403-1406 years). O. Togaev translation, responsible editor: Muhammad Ali.- T.: Uzbekistan, 2010.- B. 264.
2. Barthold V.V. It's Ulugbek's ego time. Petrograd', 1918. S. 19-36.
3. Brother Ismail. The great state of Timur. Q. Cairo translation. T.: Cholpon, 1996-5. 160.
4. G.A. Pugachenkova. Architectural heritage of Timur. Main editorial office encyclopedia, 1996 B. 127.
5. Fayziev T. Family tree of Timurids. T. Writer, Khazina, 1995. - 350 6; Fayziev T. Family tree of Timurids. Reprint. T.: Info Capital Group, 2020 364 6.
6. Yusupova D. Jizn i trudy Khondamira. T.: Science, 2006. B. 34-44 7.
7. Buriev O. Central Asia in the written sources of the Timurid era (historical geographical maps) T.: Uzbekistan, 1997. - B. 166.
8. Абдуносирова О. Шоҳрух мирзонинг илмий ва ижодий қарашлари //Актуальные проблемы истории Узбекистана. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 172-179.

9. Abdunosirova O.B. ON THE SPONSORSHIP ACTIVITIES OF THE TEMURIAN PRINCE. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research 1(11), 2022.

